

EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN 5-6 GRADE PUPILS.

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Annotation: This article highlights the concepts of competence and communicative competence. It also defines the importance of developing communicative competences of 5-6th graders and its features, challenges of it and strategies to improve 5-6th graders' communicative competences.

Keywords: key features of the communicative competences, challenges of communicative competences, strategies

Communicative competence is the ability to use language effectively in a variety of social and academic contexts (Canale & Swain, 1980). It encompasses a range of skills, including listening, speaking, reading, and writing, as well as the ability to use language appropriately and effectively in different situations.

According to N.A. Muslimov, competence is a set of knowledge, skills, qualifications and personal qualities necessary for professional activity in the relevant field.

D.Pulatova mentioned that communicative competence is the ability to achieve communicative goals in a socially appropriate manner. It is organized and goal-oriented, meaning the ability to select and apply appropriate and effective skills in an appropriate context. It includes oral and written communication behaviors. Communicative competence refers to students' ability to use a foreign language to communicate.

Developing communicative competence is essential for success in school and in life. 5-6th grade pupils with strong communicative skills are better able to learn new

information, collaborate with others, and solve problems. They are also more likely to be successful in their careers and personal relationships.

The following are some of the key features of the communicative competences of 5–6 th grade students, according to the research literature:

- **Listening comprehension:** 5–6th grade students should be able to listen actively to a variety of spoken texts, such as teacher lectures, class discussions, and audio recordings (Celce-Murcia & Olshtain, 2006). They should be able to identify the main points of the text, understand supporting details, and draw inferences (Derewiany, 2011).

- **Speaking fluency:** 5–6th grade students should be able to speak fluently and clearly on a variety of topics. They should be able to use a variety of sentence structures and vocabulary, and they should be able to adapt their speech to the situation (Celce-Murcia & Olshtain, 2006).

- **Reading comprehension:** 5–6th grade students should be able to read a variety of texts, such as fiction, non-fiction, and poetry. They should be able to identify the main ideas of the text, understand supporting details, and analyze the author's purpose (Derewiany, 2011).

- **Writing fluency:** 5–6th grade students should be able to write fluently and clearly on a variety of topics. They should be able to use a variety of sentence structures and vocabulary, and they should be able to organize their thoughts in a logical way (Celce-Murcia & Olshtain, 2006).

- **Vocabulary knowledge:** 5–6th grade students should have a strong vocabulary base. They should be able to understand and use a variety of words in different contexts (Derewiany, 2011).

- **Grammar knowledge:** 5–6th grade students should have a good understanding of grammar rules. They should be able to use grammar correctly in their writing and speaking (Celce-Murcia & Olshtain, 2006).

- **Pragmatic competence:** 5–6th grade students should have a good understanding of how to use language appropriately in different social situations.

They should be able to use different registers of language, such as formal and informal language, and they should be able to adapt their language to the audience (Celce-Murcia & Olshtain, 2006).

- **Sociocultural competence:** 5–6th grade students should have a good understanding of different cultures and how to communicate effectively with people from different cultures (Derewiany, 2011).

It is important to note that all of these features of communicative competence are interrelated. For example, in order to be able to speak fluently, students need to have a strong vocabulary base and a good understanding of grammar rules. Similarly, in order to be able to write effectively, students need to have a good understanding of grammar rules and pragmatic competence.

Teachers can play a vital role in helping 5–6th grade students develop their communicative competences. By providing students with opportunities to practice communicating in a variety of contexts and by teaching students about different communication strategies, teachers can help students become more effective communicators.

Developing communicative competences in 5–6th graders is a challenging task, but it is essential for their success in school and in life. Here are some of the challenges that 5–6 graders may face in developing their communicative competences:

- **Lack of motivation:** Some students may not be motivated to develop their communicative competences. They may not see the need for it, or they may find it difficult or boring.

- **Limited opportunities to practice:** Students may not have enough opportunities to practice communicating in a variety of contexts. This may be due to a number of factors, such as large class sizes, limited resources, or a lack of emphasis on communication in the curriculum.

- **Language barriers:** Students who are learning English as a second language (ESL) may face additional challenges in developing their communicative

competences. They may need to learn new vocabulary and grammar structures, and they may need to practice speaking and writing in English more frequently.

- **Lack of confidence:** Some students may lack confidence in their ability to communicate effectively. This may be due to a number of factors, such as previous negative experiences, shyness, or a lack of support from teachers and peers.

- **Difficulty with specific components of communicative competence:** Students may also face specific challenges in developing each of the four components of communicative competence: listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

Here are some references that support the above challenges:

- **Motivation:** A study by Dörnyei (2009) found that motivation is a key factor in the development of communicative competence. Students who are motivated to learn are more likely to put in the effort necessary to develop their communicative skills.

- **Opportunities to practice:** A study by Swain (1985) found that students who have more opportunities to practice communicating are more likely to develop their communicative competence. This is because practice allows students to experiment with different communication strategies and learn from their mistakes.

- **Language barriers:** A study by Collier and Thomas (1991) found that ESL students face a number of challenges in developing their communicative competence, including limited vocabulary and grammar knowledge, difficulty understanding different types of accents, and a lack of confidence in their ability to communicate effectively.

- **Lack of confidence:** A study by MacIntyre and Gardner (1991) found that students who lack confidence in their ability to communicate effectively are less likely to participate in classroom activities and to take risks in their communication.

- **Difficulty with specific components of communicative competence:** A study by Celce-Murcia and Olshtain (2006) found that students may face specific challenges in developing each of the four components of communicative competence:

listening, speaking, reading, and writing. For example, students may have difficulty listening actively to spoken texts, speaking fluently and clearly, understanding different types of written texts, or writing fluently and clearly.

Despite the challenges, there are a number of things that teachers can do to help 5–6 graders develop their communicative competences. There are a number of effective strategies for developing communicative competence in 5–6th grade students. One important strategy is to provide students with opportunities to practice communicating in a variety of contexts. This can be done through classroom discussions, group projects, and presentations. It is also important to provide students with feedback on their communication skills so that they can learn from their mistakes and improve their performance.

1. Collaborative Group Work: Encourage students to work in small groups to engage in discussions, problem-solving, and peer feedback. This strategy promotes active participation and develops communicative skills. (Johnson, D.W., Johnson, R.T., & Smith, K.A. 2014)

2. Role-Play and Drama Activities: Engage students in role-playing scenarios or drama activities to encourage improvisation and active communication. This strategy enhances their oral communication skills and builds their confidence. (Wright, A., Betteridge, D., & Buckby, M. 2005)

3. Authentic Materials: Use real-life materials, such as newspapers, magazines, and online articles, to promote reading and comprehension skills. Encourage students to discuss and reflect on the content, facilitating communication and critical thinking. (Ur, P. 1996)

4. Reciprocal Teaching: Utilize the "Fab Four" strategies (predicting, questioning, clarifying, summarizing) to guide students' comprehension of textual information. This method enhances reading and speaking skills through dialogue and collaboration. (Palinscar, A.S., & Brown, A.L. 1984)

5. Writing Journals: Encourage students to maintain personal writing journals, where they can freely express their thoughts and ideas. This strategy improves their

written communication skills and fosters self-reflection. (Graham, S., & Hebert, M. 2011)

There are a number of reasons why it is so important for 5-6 graders to develop their communicative competences. First, communicative competence is essential for academic success. Students who are able to communicate effectively are better able to learn new information, collaborate with others, and solve problems. Second, communicative competence is essential for social success. Students who are able to communicate effectively are better able to build relationships, resolve conflicts, and express their needs and desires. Third, communicative competence is essential for career success. In today's globalized world, employees need to be able to communicate effectively with people from a variety of backgrounds and cultures.

There are a number of things that teachers can do to help students in 5-6 grades develop their communicative competences. First, they can create a supportive and collaborative learning environment where students feel comfortable taking risks and communicating their ideas. Second, they can provide students with opportunities to practice communicating in a variety of contexts, such as through classroom discussions, group projects, and presentations. Third, they can teach students about different communication strategies, such as how to listen actively, how to speak clearly and concisely, and how to write effectively. Finally, they can provide students with feedback on their communication skills so that they can learn from their mistakes and improve their performance.

References:

- 1. Canale, M., & Swain, M. (1980). Theoretical perspectives on communicative competence. *Applied linguistics*, 1(1), 1-47.
- 2. Celce-Murcia, M., & Olshtain, E. (2006). *Discourse and context in language teaching: A guide for educators*. Cambridge University Press.
- 3. Derewiany, W. (2011). *Language teaching methodology: A textbook for teachers*. Nelson Education.

- 4. Dornyei, Z. and Ushioda, E. (2009) *Motivation, Language Identity and the L2 Self*. Channel View Publications, Bristol.
- 5. Graham, S., & Hebert, M. (2011). *Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness: Self-Regulated Strategy Development at Tier 2 for Second-Grade Students With Writing and Behavioral Difficulties: A Randomized Controlled Trial*.
- 6. Johnson, D.W., Johnson, R.T. and Smith, K. (2014) *Cooperative Learning Improving University Instruction by Basing Practice on Validated Theory*
- 7. MacIntyre, P. D, & Gardner, R. C. (1991). *Methods and results in the study of anxiety and language learning*.
- 8. Muslimov.N.A., Abdullateva Q.M., Qo'ysinov O.A., Gaipova N.S. *Kasb ta'limi o'qituvchilarning kasbiy kompetentligini shakllantirish texnologiyasi.Monografiya.-T."Fan va texnologiya".2013*
- 9. Palinscar, A.S., & Brown, A.L.(1984). *Cognition and Instruction : Reciprocal Teaching of Comprehension-Fostering and Comprehension-Monitoring Activities*.
- 10. Pulatova D.R. *Intensiv ta'lim texnologiyalari asosida nofilologik ta'lim yo'nalishi talabalarini kommunikativ kompetensiyalarini takomillashtirish, 2021. B 20-23*
- 11. Swain, M. (1985). *Communicative Competence: Some roles of Comprehensible Input and Comprehensible Output in its Development*.
- 12. Ur, P. (1996) *A course in Language Teaching: Practice and Theory*.Cambridge University Press, Cambridge
- 13. Wright, A., Betteridge, D., & Buckby, M. (2006). *Games for Language Learning (3rd ed.)*. Cambridge Cambridge University Press.